

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322696043>

Thermal bridge free Passive House foundation design in the Romanian seismic region

Conference Paper · April 2017

CITATION

1

READS

2,310

5 authors, including:

Szabolcs Varga

Technical University of Cluj-Napoca

8 PUBLICATIONS 14 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Horia Petran

Institutul Național de Cercetare-Dezvoltare în Construcții, Urbanism și Dezvoltare...

36 PUBLICATIONS 136 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Ancuța Maria Măgurean

Technical University of Cluj-Napoca

20 PUBLICATIONS 30 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Marian-Ciprian Niculuță

Institutul Național de Cercetare-Dezvoltare în Construcții, Urbanism și Dezvoltare...

4 PUBLICATIONS 28 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Thermal bridge free passive house foundation design in the Romanian seismic region

Szabolcs Varga, PhD, V&V Projekt srl
str. Gödri Ferenc, nr. 2/31, Sfântu Gheorghe, Romania
Phone: +40 (0) 740 842 810; varga.szabolcs@vvp.ro

Horia Petran, PhD, National Institute for Research & Development URBAN-INCERC
Ancuța Măgurean, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Norana Petre, Atelier 1
Marian Niculuță, National Institute for Research & Development URBAN-INCERC

Introduction

At the present, there are only 4 Romanian certified passive houses and also few in certification phase. In order to spread the passive house concept in the country, there is a need for simple construction details, materials that can be locally bought, and also which comply with the rigorous seismic design provisions. This article focuses on confined masonry buildings, which are amongst the most structural systems used in Romania.

Analysis

Construction details of a slab on the ground in a heated basement (details D1 and D4), a slab on the ground without basement (D2; D5), and a slab above an unheated basement (D3; D6) were assessed using software Therm. The methodologies used are prescribed in ISO standards 10211 & 13370 [ISO, 2007],[ISO, 2008] and online sources [Passipedia, 2016].

Figure 1: Isotherms distribution and linear thermal bridges for structural details of passive house foundations widely accepted in Romania

Figure 1 presents isothermal diagrams and linear thermal bridges for passive house foundation details widely accepted by the Romanian engineering community, while Figure 2 depicts the same data for optimised details proposed by the authors of the present study,

with reference to exterior dimensions. The latter thermal insulation is generally placed over the slab on the ground/above the unheated basement, while the first cellular clay blocks are filled with perlite [Online, 2014] and insulating mortar is used above and below the first masonry blocks. It should be mentioned that – in the case of confined masonry buildings - Romanian seismic provisions [UTCB, 2013] prescribe the use of materials characterised by high compressive strength, in consequence, materials like aerated concrete blocks or foam glass aren't accepted in this context.

Figure 2: Isotherms distribution and linear thermal bridges for the optimised details

Conclusions

If one would choose to use the “widely accepted” details for an average size passive house project, the heating demand could be increased by approx. $4\text{kWh/m}^2/\text{a}$, according to PHPP. Further structural investigations are needed for interrupting the reinforced concrete (RC) shear walls of the heated basement (detail D1). As thermal breaking of the structural elements of the infrastructure is not generally accepted, placing the insulation over the RC slab on the ground leads to details with smaller thermal bridges. The latter conclusion is valid also for moment resisting RC frame structures. Thus, the proposed details are suitable for their use in cost-effective passive house projects, since they are made up of affordable materials, which can be locally purchased.

References

- [ISO 2007] ISO, EN 10211: *Thermal bridges in building construction–Heat flows and surface temperatures–detailed calculations*, 2007.
- [ISO 2008] ISO, EN 13370: *Thermal performance of buildings. Heat transfer via the ground. Calculation methods*, 2008.
- [Passipedia 2016] *Thermal bridge calculation*. [ONLINE] Available at: https://passipedia.org/basics/building_physics/_basics/thermal_bridges/tbcalculation. [Accessed 10 January 2017].
- [Online 2014] *Fußpunktlösung(Thermofuß)bei energieeffizienten Gebäuden*. [ONLINE] Available at http://www.winklerbaumaterialien.at/letolt/katalogus/wienerberger_thermofus_s.pdf. [Accessed 10 January 2017]. Wienerberger. 2014.

[UTCB 2013]

Seismic design code – Part I. Design provisions for buildings (in Romanian).
Technical University of Bucharest [UTCB], 2013.

Abstract

Optimised details of a slab on the ground in a heated basement, a slab on the ground without a basement, and a slab above an unheated basement were assessed. The proposed details are suitable for their use in cost-effective passive house projects since they are made up of affordable materials, can be locally purchased, and which comply with the rigorous Romanian seismic provisions.